

A NOTE ON THE PREPARATION OF ALKALINE EARTH NITRITES

BY T. M. OZA AND N. L. DIPALI

Preparation of alkaline earth nitrites, particularly of barium nitrite, is important as the latter is used in the preparation of other nitrites. Nitrites of barium, strontium and calcium have been prepared, but the methods used are not adaptable to quick preparation in large amounts. The method has therefore been modified by us to suit these requirements. A further advantage of the modified method lies in yielding the salts in extra pure state.

P. C. Ray (*I. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 177) prepared pure barium nitrite using molecular proportions of silver nitrite and barium chloride, their saturated solutions in water, mixing, agitating vigorously to coagulate the silver chloride formed, and evaporating the filtrate nearly to dryness on a water-bath. The nitrite thus prepared was found by us to contain traces of nitrate which persisted even after two recrystallisations. This is presumably formed by autoxidation of the nitrite during evaporation of the large bulk of the solution; silver nitrite is very sparingly soluble in water.

To reduce the bulk of the solution we have substituted water by ammonia, diluted half with water, as the solvent for silver nitrite. To the concentrated solution of silver nitrite in such ammonia, a solution of the alkaline earth chloride in water is added, the mixture agitated and the ammonia then boiled off. The dissolved nitrite is then recovered either by evaporation in a desiccator or by treatment with alcohol. The analyses of the nitrites of calcium, strontium and barium, prepared by this method, are given below. The strontium and calcium nitrite did not part with their water of crystallisation even on intensive desiccation.

Calcium nitrite: 0.0750 g. and 0.0878 g. gave respectively 0.0658 g. and 0.0804 g. CaSO_4 . [Found: Ca, 0.01968 g. and 0.02362 g. respectively *i.e.*, 26.23% and 26.91%. Calc. for $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_2)_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$: Ca, 26.66%].

0.0685 g. and 0.0412 g. of the substance consumed 41.5 c.c. and 25.0 c.c. of 0.05*N*- KMnO_4 . [Found: NO_2' , 61.25% and 61.35% respectively. Calc. for $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_2)_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$: NO_2' , 61.3%]

Strontium nitrite: 0.1133 g. and 0.0924 g. gave 0.1056 g. and 0.0862 g. of SrSO_4 . [Found: Sr, 0.05037 g. and 0.04111 g. respectively, *i.e.*, 44.46% and 44.49%. Calc. for $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_2)_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$: Sr, 44.32%].

0.0225 g. and 0.0280 g. of the substance consumed 4.575 c.c. and 5.725 c.c. of 0.1002*N*- KMnO_4 . [Found: NO_2' , 0.01054 g. and 0.01319 g. respectively, *i.e.*, 46.85% and 47.11%. Calc. for $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_2)_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$: NO_2' , 46.56%].

Barium nitrite : 2.386 g. gave 2.2104 g. anhydrous substance. Loss per 229 g. $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_2)_2$ would therefore be 18.19 g. *i.e.*, one molecule water ; 0.1997 g. and 0.1811 g. of anhydrous substance gave 0.2028 g. and 0.1845 g. BaSO_4 . [Found : Ba, 0.1194 g. and 0.1086 g. respectively, *i.e.*, 59.77% and 59.98%. Calc. for $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_2)_2$: Ba, 59.89%].

0.0899 g. and 0.0602 g. of the substance consumed 15.80 c.c., and 10.65 c.c., of 0.09951N- KMnO_4 . [Found : NO_2' , 0.03616 g. and 0.02438 g. respectively, *i.e.*, 40.23% and 40.5%. Calc. for $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_2)_2$: NO_2' , 40.11%]

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENTS,
GUJARAT COLLEGE, AHMEDABAD
AND
KARNATAK COLLEGE, DHARWAR.

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